

PERMUTATION PATTERNS OF THE ITERATED SYRACUSE FUNCTION

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Received: 8/1/23, Accepted: 11/2/23, Published: 5/27/24

Abstract

Let Ω be the set of odd positive integers and let $S : \Omega \rightarrow \Omega$ be the Syracuse function. It is proved that, for every permutation σ of $(1, 2, 3)$, the set of triples of the form $(m, S(m), S^2(m))$ with permutation pattern σ has positive density, and these densities are computed. However, there exist permutations τ of $(1, 2, 3, 4)$ such that no quadruple $(m, S(m), S^2(m), S^3(m))$ has permutation pattern τ . This implies the nonexistence of certain permutation patterns of n -tuples $(m, S(m), \dots, S^{n-1}(m))$ for all $n \geq 4$.

1. Permutation Patterns

Let Ω be the set of odd positive integers. The *Syracuse function* is the arithmetic function $S : \Omega \rightarrow \Omega$ defined by

$$S(m) = \frac{3m + 1}{2^e}$$

where e is the largest integer such that 2^e divides $3m + 1$. Equivalently, $S(m)$ is the *odd part*, that is, the largest odd divisor, of the even integer $3m + 1$. Note that $S(m) = 1$ if and only if $m = \sum_{i=0}^k 4^i = (4^{k+1} - 1)/3$ for some nonnegative integer k . The notorious *Collatz conjecture* asserts that for every positive integer m there exists an integer r such that $S^r(m) = 1$ (Lagarias [3], Tao [9], Wikipedia [11]). By supercomputer calculation, Barina [2] has verified the conjecture for all $m < 2^{68}$.

An arithmetic function is any function whose domain is a nonempty subset Ω of the set positive integers. Let $S : \Omega \rightarrow \Omega$ be an arithmetic function and, for $j \in \mathbf{N}$, let $S^j : \Omega \rightarrow \Omega$ be the j th iterate of S . Let $V = (v_i)_{i=1}^n$ be a finite sequence of positive integers. We say that an integer m in Ω has *increasing-decreasing pattern* V with respect to S if

$$m < S(m) < S^2(m) < \dots < S^{v_1}(m)$$

$$S^{v_1}(m) > S^{v_1+1}(m) > \dots > S^{v_1+v_2}(m)$$

$$S^{v_1+v_2}(m) < S^{v_1+v_2+1}(m) < \dots < S^{v_1+v_2+v_3}(m)$$

and, in general, if i is odd, then

$$S^{v_1+\dots+v_{i-1}}(m) < S^{v_1+\dots+v_{i-1}+1}(m) < \dots < S^{v_1+\dots+v_{i-1}+v_i}(m) \tag{1}$$

and if i is even, then

$$S^{v_1+\dots+v_{i-1}}(m) > S^{v_1+\dots+v_{i-1}+1}(m) > \dots > S^{v_1+\dots+v_{i-1}+v_i}(m). \tag{2}$$

The arithmetic function S is *wildly increasing-decreasing* if, for every finite sequence V of positive integers, there exists an integer $m \in \Omega$ such that m has increasing-decreasing pattern V with respect to S .

Nathanson [4] proved that the Syracuse function is wildly increasing-decreasing. In this paper we consider more subtle variations in successive iterates of the Syracuse function.

Let Σ_n be the group of permutations of $\{1, 2, 3, \dots, n\}$. Let $X = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$ be an n -tuple of distinct real numbers. We rearrange the coordinates of X to obtain an n -tuple (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n) such that

$$y_1 < y_2 < \dots < y_n.$$

There is a unique permutation $\sigma \in \Sigma_n$ such that

$$(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = (y_{\sigma(1)}, y_{\sigma(2)}, \dots, y_{\sigma(n)}).$$

We call σ the *permutation pattern* of the n -tuple X and denote it by $(\sigma(1), \sigma(2), \dots, \sigma(n))$. In standard form, this is the permutation $(\sigma(a) \ \sigma(2) \ \dots \ \sigma(n))$.

For example, if

$$X = (x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4) = (7, 13, 18, 11)$$

then

$$7 < 11 < 13 < 18.$$

We obtain

$$(y_1, y_2, y_3, y_4) = (7, 11, 13, 18).$$

and

$$(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4) = (y_1, y_3, y_4, y_2).$$

The permutation pattern of the quadruple $(7, 13, 18, 11)$ is $\sigma = (1, 3, 4, 2)$.

It is an open problem to determine, for every positive integer n , the possible permutation patterns of the initial segments $(m, S(m), S^2(m), \dots, S^{n-1}(m))$ of the iterated Syracuse function for integers $m \in \Omega$ such that $S^i(m) \neq S^j(m)$ for $0 \leq i < j \leq n - 1$. For every permutation $\sigma \in \Sigma_n$, let $\Gamma_\sigma(M)$ count the number of odd

positive integers $m \leq M$ such that the n -tuple $(m, S(m), S^2(m), \dots, S^{n-1}(m))$ has distinct coordinates and has permutation pattern σ . The *permutation density* of $\sigma \in \Sigma_n$ is

$$d_n(\sigma) = \lim_{M \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\Gamma_\sigma(M)}{M/2}$$

(if the limit exists).

In this paper we prove that every permutation $\sigma \in \Sigma_3$ occurs with positive density. We also prove that there are permutations $\tau \in \Sigma_4$ such that τ not only has zero permutation density, but there exists no positive integer m with permutation pattern τ . If no n -tuple $(m, S(m), S^2(m), \dots, S^{n-1}(m))$ has permutation pattern $(a_1, \dots, a_n) \in \Sigma_n$, then no $(n+1)$ -tuple $(m, S(m), S^2(m), \dots, S^{n-1}(m), S^n(m))$ has permutation pattern $(a_1, \dots, a_n, n+1) \in \Sigma_{n+1}$. It follows that, for all $n \geq 4$, there exist permutations τ in Σ_n such that no n -tuple $(m, S(m), S^2(m), \dots, S^{n-1}(m))$ has permutation pattern τ .

Theorem 1. *The following table gives the density of permutation patterns of triples $(m, S(m), S^2(m))$.*

<i>permutation pattern $\sigma \in \Sigma_3$</i>	<i>permutation density $d_3(\sigma)$</i>
(1, 2, 3)	1/4
(1, 3, 2)	1/8
(2, 1, 3)	1/8
(2, 3, 1)	1/8
(3, 1, 2)	1/8
(3, 2, 1)	1/4

The proof of this result will follow immediately from Theorems 3 and 4 below.

Note: In the study of the Collatz conjecture, instead of the Syracuse function, investigators often use the Collatz functions

$$C(m) = \begin{cases} 3m + 1 & \text{if } m \text{ is odd} \\ \frac{m}{2} & \text{if } m \text{ is even} \end{cases}$$

and

$$C_1(m) = \begin{cases} \frac{3m+1}{2} & \text{if } m \text{ is odd} \\ \frac{m}{2} & \text{if } m \text{ is even.} \end{cases}$$

The equivalent Collatz conjectures state that for every odd integer m there exist positive integers n and n_1 such that $C^n(m) = 1$ and $C_1^{n_1}(m) = 1$. Simons and de Weger [8] and Simons [5, 6, 7] have studied a different kind of increasing-decreasing behavior for the Collatz function. Albert, Gudmundsson, and Ulfarsson [1] considered permutations generated by the iterated function $C(m)$.

2. Permutation Patterns for Pairs

We begin with a simple but important calculation of permutation densities for pairs.

Theorem 2. *Let $m \in \Omega$. If $m \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$, then $(m, S(m))$ has permutation pattern $(1, 2)$. If $m \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$ and $m > 1$, then $(m, S(m))$ has permutation pattern $(2, 1)$.*

<i>congruence class of m</i>	<i>permutation pattern $\sigma \in \Sigma_2$</i>	<i>permutation density $d_3(\sigma)$</i>
$3 \pmod{4}$	$(1, 2)$	$1/2$
$1 \pmod{4}$	$(2, 1)$	$1/2$

Proof. If $m = 3 + 4x$ for some nonnegative integer x , then $3m + 1 = 10 + 12x$ and

$$S(m) = \frac{10 + 12x}{2} = 5 + 6x > 3 + 4x = m.$$

Thus, $(m, S(m))$ has permutation pattern $(1, 2)$.

If $m = 1 + 4x$ for some positive integer x , then $3m + 1 = 4 + 12x$ and there is an integer $e \geq 2$ such that

$$S(m) = \frac{4 + 12x}{2^e} = \frac{1 + 3x}{2^{e-2}} \leq 1 + 3x < 1 + 4x = m$$

and $(m, S(m))$ has permutation pattern $(2, 1)$. This completes the proof. □

Corollary 1. *Let A be the set of odd positive integers m for which the permutation pattern of the triple $(m, S(m), S^2(m))$ is*

$$(1, 2, 3), \quad (1, 3, 2), \quad \text{or} \quad (2, 3, 1).$$

Let B be the set of odd positive integers m for which the permutation pattern of the triple $(m, S(m), S^2(m))$ is

$$(2, 1, 3), \quad (3, 1, 2), \quad \text{or} \quad (3, 2, 1).$$

The set A has density $1/2$ and the set B has density $1/2$.

Proof. The pair $(m, S(m))$ has permutation pattern $(1, 2)$ if and only if the triple $(m, S(m), S^2(m))$ has permutation pattern $(1, 2, 3)$, $(1, 3, 2)$, or $(2, 3, 1)$. Similarly, the pair $(m, S(m))$ has permutation pattern $(2, 1)$ if and only if the triple $(m, S(m), S^2(m))$ has permutation pattern $(2, 1, 3)$, $(3, 1, 2)$, or $(3, 2, 1)$. This completes the proof. □

3. Permutation Patterns for Triples for $m \not\equiv 5 \pmod{8}$

The calculation of permutation densities for triples $(m, S(m), S^2(m))$ is divided into two cases. In the first case we consider odd positive integers $m \not\equiv 5 \pmod{8}$ and in the second case we consider odd positive integers $m \equiv 5 \pmod{8}$.

Theorem 3. *Every odd positive integer m such that $m \not\equiv 5 \pmod{8}$ belongs to exactly one of the five congruence classes in the table below. Each congruence class uniquely determines the permutation pattern of the triple $(m, S(m), S^2(m))$ for all integers $m > 1$ in the congruence class.*

congruence class of m	permutation pattern $\sigma \in \Sigma_3$	permutation density $d_3(\sigma)$
$7 \pmod{8}$	$(1, 2, 3)$	$1/4$
$9 \pmod{16}$	$(2, 1, 3)$	$1/8$
$11 \pmod{16}$	$(1, 3, 2)$	$1/8$
$3 \pmod{16}$	$(2, 3, 1)$	$1/8$
$1 \pmod{16}$	$(3, 2, 1)$	$1/8$

Proof. The following diagram shows the five congruence classes (in black boxes) that partition the integers $m \not\equiv 5 \pmod{8}$ and the “missing” congruence class $5 \pmod{8}$ (in the red box).

If $m \equiv 7 \pmod{8}$, then for some nonnegative integer x we have

$$\begin{aligned} m &= 7 + 8x \\ S(m) &= \frac{22 + 24x}{2} = 11 + 12x \\ S^2(m) &= \frac{34 + 36x}{2} = 17 + 18x \end{aligned}$$

and

$$7 + 8x < 11 + 12x < 17 + 18x.$$

Therefore, $(m, S(m), S^2(m))$ has permutation pattern $(1, 2, 3)$.

If $m \equiv 9 \pmod{16}$, then for some nonnegative integer x we have

$$\begin{aligned} m &= 9 + 16x \\ S(m) &= \frac{28 + 48x}{4} = 7 + 12x \\ S^2(m) &= \frac{22 + 36x}{2} = 11 + 18x \end{aligned}$$

and

$$7 + 12x < 9 + 16x < 11 + 18x.$$

Therefore, $(m, S(m), S^2(m))$ has permutation pattern $(2, 1, 3)$.

If $m \equiv 11 \pmod{16}$, then for some nonnegative integer x we have

$$\begin{aligned} m &= 11 + 16x \\ S(m) &= \frac{34 + 48x}{2} = 17 + 24x \\ S^2(m) &= \frac{52 + 72x}{4} = 13 + 18x \end{aligned}$$

and

$$11 + 16x < 13 + 18x < 17 + 24x.$$

Therefore, $(m, S(m), S^2(m))$ has permutation pattern $(1, 3, 2)$.

If $m \equiv 3 \pmod{16}$, then for some positive integer x and nonnegative integer e we have

$$\begin{aligned} m &= 3 + 16x \\ S(m) &= \frac{10 + 48x}{2} = 5 + 24x \\ S^2(m) &= \frac{16 + 72x}{8} = \frac{2 + 9x}{2^e}. \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\frac{2 + 9x}{2^e} \leq 2 + 9x < 3 + 16x < 5 + 24x.$$

Therefore, $(m, S(m), S^2(m))$ has permutation pattern $(2, 3, 1)$.

If $m > 1$ and $m \equiv 1 \pmod{16}$, then for some positive integer x and nonnegative integer e we have

$$\begin{aligned} m &= 1 + 16x \\ S(m) &= \frac{4 + 48x}{4} = 1 + 12x \\ S^2(m) &= \frac{4 + 36x}{4} = \frac{1 + 9x}{2^e}. \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\frac{1 + 9x}{2^e} \leq 1 + 9x < 1 + 12x < 1 + 16x.$$

Therefore, $(m, S(m), S^2(m))$ has permutation pattern $(3, 2, 1)$. This completes the proof. \square

4. Permutation Patterns for Triples for $m \equiv 5 \pmod{8}$

We shall prove that half of the odd positive integers congruent to $5 \pmod{8}$ have the 3-term permutation pattern $(3, 2, 1)$ and half have the 3-term permutation pattern $(3, 1, 2)$.

In the following proofs, e denotes a nonnegative integer.

Lemma 1. *Let $k \geq 1$. If m is a positive integer and*

$$m \equiv \sum_{i=0}^k 4^i + 2 \cdot 4^k \pmod{2 \cdot 4^{k+1}}$$

then $m \equiv 5 \pmod{8}$ and the permutation pattern of $(m, S(m), S^2(m))$ is $(3, 2, 1)$.

Proof. For some nonnegative integer x we have

$$m = \frac{4^{k+1} - 1}{3} + 2 \cdot 4^k + 2 \cdot 4^{k+1}x \geq 13 + 32x$$

and

$$3m + 1 = 4^{k+1} + 3 \cdot 2 \cdot 4^k + 3 \cdot 2 \cdot 4^{k+1}x.$$

It follows that

$$S(m) = \frac{3m + 1}{2 \cdot 4^k} = 5 + 12x < 13 + 32x \leq m.$$

We have

$$3S(m) + 1 = 16 + 36x = 4(4 + 9x)$$

and so

$$S^2(m) = \frac{4 + 9x}{2^e} \leq 4 + 9x < 5 + 12x = S(m).$$

Therefore,

$$S^2(m) < S(m) < m$$

and the permutation pattern of $(m, S(m), S^2(m))$ is $(3, 2, 1)$. This completes the proof. \square

Lemma 2. *Let $k \geq 1$. If m is a positive integer and*

$$m \equiv \sum_{i=0}^k 4^i \pmod{4^{k+2}}$$

then $m \equiv 5 \pmod{8}$ and either $m = \sum_{i=0}^k 4^i$ and $S(m) = S^2(m) = 1$ or the permutation pattern of $(m, S(m), S^2(m))$ is $(3, 2, 1)$.

Proof. For some nonnegative integer x we have

$$m = \frac{4^{k+1} - 1}{3} + 4^{k+2}x \geq 5 + 64x$$

and

$$3m + 1 = 4^{k+1} + 3 \cdot 4^{k+2}x.$$

If $x = 0$, then $3m + 1 = 4^{k+1}$ and $S(m) = S^2(m) = 1$.

If $x \geq 1$, then

$$S(m) = \frac{3m + 1}{4^{k+1}} = 1 + 12x < 5 + 64x \leq m$$

and

$$S^2(m) = \frac{1 + 9x}{2^e} \leq 1 + 9x < 1 + 12x = S(m).$$

Therefore,

$$S^2(m) < S(m) < m$$

and the permutation pattern of $(m, S(m), S^2(m))$ is $(3, 2, 1)$. This completes the proof. \square

Lemma 3. *Let $k \geq 1$. If m is a positive integer and*

$$m \equiv \sum_{i=0}^{k+1} 4^i + 2 \cdot 4^k \pmod{2 \cdot 4^{k+1}}$$

then $m \equiv 5 \pmod{8}$ and the permutation pattern of $(m, S(m), S^2(m))$ is $(3, 1, 2)$.

Proof. For some nonnegative integer x we have

$$m = \frac{4^{k+2} - 1}{3} + 2 \cdot 4^k + 2 \cdot 4^{k+1}x$$

$$\geq 29 + 32x$$

and

$$3m + 1 = 4^{k+2} + 3 \cdot 2 \cdot 4^k + 3 \cdot 2 \cdot 4^{k+1}x.$$

Therefore,

$$S(m) = \frac{3m + 1}{2 \cdot 4^k} = 11 + 12x$$

and

$$S^2(m) = 17 + 18x.$$

We have

$$S(m) = 11 + 12x < S^2(m) = 17 + 18x < 29 + 32x \leq m$$

and the permutation pattern of $(m, S(m), S^2(m))$ is $(3, 1, 2)$. This completes the proof. \square

Lemma 4. *Let $k \geq 1$. If m is a positive integer and*

$$m \equiv \sum_{i=0}^{k+1} 4^i + 4^{k+1} \pmod{4^{k+2}}$$

then $m \equiv 5 \pmod{8}$ and the permutation pattern of $(m, S(m), S^2(m))$ is $(3, 1, 2)$.

Proof. For some nonnegative integer x we have

$$m = \frac{4^{k+2} - 1}{3} + 4^{k+1} + 4^{k+2}x$$

$$\geq 37 + 64x$$

and

$$3m + 1 = 4^{k+2} + 3 \cdot 4^{k+1} + 3 \cdot 4^{k+2}x$$

It follows that

$$S(m) = \frac{3m + 1}{4^{k+1}} = 7 + 12x$$

and

$$S^2(m) = 11 + 18x.$$

Therefore,

$$S(m) = 7 + 12 < S^2(m) = 11 + 18x < 37 + 64x \leq m$$

and the permutation pattern of $(m, S(m), S^2(m))$ is $(3, 1, 2)$. This completes the proof. \square

Notation. Let $F(M)$ be a positive function of M . We denote by $o(F(M))$ a function $G(M)$ such that $\lim_{M \rightarrow \infty} \frac{G(M)}{F(M)} = 0$. Thus, $o(1)$ denotes a function $G(M)$ such that $\lim_{M \rightarrow \infty} G(M) = 0$. Note that $-o(1) = o(1)$ and $o(1) + o(1) = o(1)$. Also, $o(X(M)) = X(M)o(1)$.

The *counting function* of a set A of positive integers is

$$A(M) = \sum_{\substack{a \in A \\ a \leq M}} 1.$$

A subset A of a set X of positive integers has density α with respect to X if the limit

$$\lim_{M \rightarrow \infty} \frac{A(M)}{X(M)}$$

exists and equals α . Equivalently, A has density α with respect to X , denoted $d_X(A) = \alpha$, if

$$A(M) = \alpha X(M) + o(X(M)).$$

If $d_X(A) = 0$, then $A(M) = o(X(M))$.

Lemma 5. *Let X be a set of positive integers, let W be a subset of X with density $d_X(W) = \omega > 0$, and let*

$$W = R_0 \cup R_1 \cup \dots \cup R_t$$

be a partition of W . Let $\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_t$ be positive real numbers such that $\sum_{i=1}^t \alpha_i = \omega$. If $d_X(R_0) = 0$ and if, for all ε with

$$0 < \varepsilon < \min(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_t)$$

there is a subset $R_{i,\varepsilon}$ of R_i such that $d_X(R_{i,\varepsilon}) = \alpha_i - \varepsilon$, then $d_X(R_j) = \alpha_j$ for all $j \in \{1, \dots, t\}$.

Proof. Let $M \geq 1$. Because the sets R_0, R_1, \dots, R_t partition the set W , we have the counting function equation

$$W(M) = R_0(M) + R_1(M) + \dots + R_t(M).$$

The density condition $d_X(R_0) = 0$ implies

$$R_0(M) = o(X(M)).$$

Let $0 < \varepsilon < \min(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_t)$. For all $i \in \{1, \dots, t\}$, the subset condition $R_{i,\varepsilon} \subseteq R_i$ implies

$$0 \leq R_{i,\varepsilon}(M) \leq R_i(M).$$

The density condition

$$d_X(R_{i,\varepsilon}) = \lim_{M \rightarrow \infty} \frac{R_{i,\varepsilon}(M)}{X(M)} = \alpha_i - \varepsilon$$

implies

$$R_{i,\varepsilon}(M) = (\alpha_i - \varepsilon + o(1))X(M).$$

Also, $d_X(W) = \omega > 0$ implies

$$W(M) = (\omega + o(1))X(M).$$

For all $j \in \{1, \dots, t\}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} (\alpha_j - \varepsilon + o(1))X(M) &= R_{j,\varepsilon}(M) \\ &\leq R_j(M) \\ &= W(M) - \sum_{\substack{i=0 \\ i \neq j}}^t R_i(M) \\ &\leq W(M) - R_0(M) - \sum_{\substack{i=1 \\ i \neq j}}^t R_{i,\varepsilon}(M) \\ &= (\omega + o(1))X(M) - o(1)X(M) - \sum_{\substack{i=1 \\ i \neq j}}^t ((\alpha_i - \varepsilon + o(1))X(M)) \\ &= \omega X(M) - \sum_{\substack{i=1 \\ i \neq j}}^t (\alpha_i - \varepsilon)X(M) + o(1)X(M) \\ &= X(M) \left(\omega - \sum_{\substack{i=1 \\ i \neq j}}^t \alpha_i + (t-1)\varepsilon + o(1) \right) \\ &= X(M) (\alpha_j + (t-1)\varepsilon + o(1)). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$\alpha_j - \varepsilon + o(1) \leq \frac{R_j(M)}{X(M)} \leq \alpha_j + (t-1)\varepsilon + o(1)$$

for all $\varepsilon > 0$ and so

$$\alpha_j + o(1) \leq \frac{R_j(M)}{X(M)} \leq \alpha_j + o(1).$$

Thus,

$$d_X(R_j) = \lim_{M \rightarrow \infty} \frac{R_j(X(M))}{X(M)} = \alpha_j$$

for all $j \in \{1, \dots, t\}$. This completes the proof. □

Theorem 4. *Let m be a positive integer such that $m \equiv 5 \pmod{8}$. If $m = \sum_{i=0}^k 4^i$ for some $k \geq 1$, then $(m, S(m), S^2(m)) = (m, 1, 1)$. If $m \neq \sum_{i=0}^k 4^i$ for some $k \geq 1$, then the triple $(m, S(m), S^2(m))$ has permutation pattern $(3, 2, 1)$ or $(3, 1, 2)$. In the congruence class $m \equiv 5 \pmod{8}$, the permutation densities are as follows:*

permutation pattern $\sigma \in \Sigma_3$	permutation density $d_3(\sigma)$
(3, 2, 1)	1/8
(3, 1, 2)	1/8

Proof. For every positive integer k , let

$$r_k = \sum_{i=0}^k 4^i = \frac{4^{k+1} - 1}{3}$$

and let

$$\mathcal{R}_0 = \{r_k : k = 1, 2, 3, \dots\} = \{5, 21, 85, 341, 1365, \dots\}.$$

The set \mathcal{R}_0 has density zero. We have $S(m) = 1$ if and only if $m = 1$ or $m \in \mathcal{R}_0$. If $m \in \mathcal{R}_0$, then $m \equiv 5 \pmod{8}$.

Let

$$\mathcal{R}_1 = \{m \equiv 5 \pmod{8} : (m, S(m), S^2(m)) \text{ has permutation pattern } (3, 1, 2)\}$$

and

$$\mathcal{R}_2 = \{m \equiv 5 \pmod{8} : (m, S(m), S^2(m)) \text{ has permutation pattern } (3, 2, 1)\}.$$

The sets $\mathcal{R}_0, \mathcal{R}_1$, and \mathcal{R}_2 are pairwise disjoint.

Let

$$\begin{aligned} &5 \pmod{8} \setminus (\mathcal{R}_0 \cup r_{k+1} \pmod{2 \cdot 4^{k+1}}) \\ &(5 \pmod{8} \setminus \mathcal{R}_0) \setminus (r_{k+1} \pmod{2 \cdot 4^{k+1}}) \end{aligned}$$

denote the set of positive integers $m \notin \mathcal{R}_0$ such that $m \equiv 5 \pmod{8}$ but $m \not\equiv r_{k+1} \pmod{2 \cdot 4^{k+1}}$. We shall prove by induction on k that this set is partitioned into two sets, one with permutation pattern (3, 2, 1) and the other with permutation pattern (3, 1, 2), and that each of these sets has permutation density

$$\frac{1}{8} \left(1 - \frac{1}{4^k}\right).$$

We begin with the cases $k = 1$ and $k = 2$.

Here is a picture of a partition of the congruence class $5 \pmod{8}$ into disjoint unions of congruence classes:

The congruence class $5 \pmod{8} = r_1 \pmod{8}$ is the disjoint union of the following

five congruence classes (in the blue boxes):

$$\begin{aligned} &13 \pmod{32} \\ &5 \pmod{64} \\ &29 \pmod{32} \\ &37 \pmod{64} \\ &21 \pmod{32} = r_2 \pmod{32}. \end{aligned}$$

Applying Lemmas 1 and 2 with $k = 1$, we see that every positive integer (except integers $m \in \mathcal{R}_0$) in the congruence classes $13 \pmod{32}$ and $5 \pmod{64}$ has permutation pattern $(3, 2, 1)$. Applying Lemmas 3 and 4 with $k = 1$, we see that every positive integer in the congruence classes $29 \pmod{32}$ and $37 \pmod{64}$ has permutation pattern $(3, 1, 2)$. Thus, the set of positive integers $m \notin \mathcal{R}_0$ in

$$5 \pmod{8} \setminus 21 \pmod{32} = 5 \pmod{8} \setminus r_2 \pmod{2 \cdot 4^2}$$

is partitioned into two sets, one with permutation pattern $(3, 2, 1)$ and the other with permutation pattern $(3, 1, 2)$. Each of these sets has density

$$\sum_{i=4}^5 \frac{1}{2^i} = \frac{1}{8} \left(1 - \frac{1}{4} \right).$$

The congruence class $21 \pmod{32} = r_2 \pmod{32}$ is the disjoint union of the following five congruence classes (in the green boxes):

$$\begin{aligned} &53 \pmod{128} \\ &21 \pmod{256} \\ &117 \pmod{128} \\ &149 \pmod{256} \\ &85 \pmod{128} = r_3 \pmod{128}. \end{aligned}$$

Applying Lemmas 1 and 2 with $k = 2$, we see that every positive integer $m \notin \mathcal{R}_0$ in the congruence classes $53 \pmod{128}$ and $21 \pmod{256}$ has permutation pattern $(3, 2, 1)$. Applying Lemmas 3 and 4 with $k = 2$, we see that every positive integer in the congruence classes $117 \pmod{128}$ and $149 \pmod{256}$ has permutation pattern $(3, 1, 2)$. Thus, the set of positive integers $m \notin \mathcal{R}_0$ in

$$21 \pmod{32} \setminus 85 \pmod{128} = r_2 \pmod{2 \cdot 4^2} \setminus r_3 \pmod{2 \cdot 4^3}$$

is partitioned into two sets, one with permutation pattern $(3, 2, 1)$ and the other with permutation pattern $(3, 1, 2)$. Each of these sets has density

$$\sum_{i=6}^7 \frac{1}{2^i} = \frac{1}{8} \left(\frac{1}{4} - \frac{1}{4^2} \right).$$

It follows that the set of positive integers $m \notin \mathcal{R}_0$ in

$$5 \pmod{8} \setminus 85 \pmod{128} = 5 \pmod{8} \setminus r_3 \pmod{2 \cdot 4^3}$$

is partitioned into two sets, one with permutation pattern (3, 2, 1) and the other with permutation pattern (3, 1, 2). Each of these sets has density

$$\frac{1}{8} \left(1 - \frac{1}{4^2} \right).$$

Let $k \geq 3$ and assume that the set of positive integers $m \notin \mathcal{R}_0$ in

$$5 \pmod{8} \setminus r_k \pmod{2 \cdot 4^k}$$

is partitioned into two sets, one with permutation pattern (3, 2, 1) and the other with permutation pattern (3, 1, 2), and that each of these sets has density

$$\frac{1}{8} \left(1 - \frac{1}{4^{k-1}} \right).$$

The following diagram displays the partition of the “red” congruence class $r_k \pmod{2 \cdot 4^k}$ into three “blue” congruence classes modulo $2 \cdot 4^{k+1}$ and two “blue” congruence classes modulo 4^{k+2} .

The congruence class $r_k \pmod{2 \cdot 4^k}$ is the disjoint union of the following five congruence classes:

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{i=0}^k 4^i + 2 \cdot 4^k \pmod{2 \cdot 4^{k+1}} \\ & \sum_{i=0}^k 4^i \pmod{4^{k+2}} \\ & \sum_{i=0}^{k+1} 4^i + 2 \cdot 4^k \pmod{2 \cdot 4^{k+1}} \\ & \sum_{i=0}^{k+1} 4^i + 4^{k+1} \pmod{4^{k+2}} \\ & \sum_{i=0}^{k+1} 4^i \pmod{2 \cdot 4^{k+1}}. \end{aligned}$$

Applying Lemmas 1 and 2, we see that every positive integer in the congruence classes $\sum_{i=0}^k 4^i + 2 \cdot 4^k \pmod{2 \cdot 4^{k+1}}$ and $\sum_{i=0}^k 4^i \pmod{4^{k+2}}$ has permutation pattern $(3, 2, 1)$. Applying Lemmas 3 and 4, we see that every positive integer in the congruence classes $\sum_{i=0}^{k+1} 4^i + 2 \cdot 4^k \pmod{2 \cdot 4^{k+1}}$ and $\sum_{i=0}^{k+1} 4^i + 4^{k+1} \pmod{4^{k+2}}$ has permutation pattern $(3, 1, 2)$. Thus, the positive integers in the set

$$r_k \pmod{2 \cdot 4^k} \setminus r_{k+1} \pmod{2 \cdot 4^{k+1}}$$

are partitioned into two sets, one with permutation pattern $(3, 2, 1)$ and the other with permutation pattern $(3, 1, 2)$. Each of these sets has density

$$\frac{1}{4^{k+1}} + \frac{2}{4^{k+2}} = \frac{1}{8} \left(\frac{1}{4^{k-1}} - \frac{1}{4^k} \right).$$

Thus, the positive integers in

$$\begin{aligned} & 5 \pmod{8} \setminus r_{k+1} \pmod{2 \cdot 4^{k+1}} \\ & = (5 \pmod{8} \setminus r_k \pmod{2 \cdot 4^k}) \cup (r_k \pmod{2 \cdot 4^k} \setminus r_{k+1} \pmod{2 \cdot 4^{k+1}}) \end{aligned}$$

are partitioned into two sets, one with permutation pattern $(3, 2, 1)$ and the other with permutation pattern $(3, 1, 2)$. Each of these sets has density

$$\frac{1}{8} \left(1 - \frac{1}{4^{k-1}} \right) + \frac{1}{8} \left(\frac{1}{4^{k-1}} - \frac{1}{4^k} \right) = \frac{1}{8} \left(1 - \frac{1}{4^k} \right).$$

This completes the induction.

For every $\varepsilon > 0$ there is an integer k such that $1/(8 \cdot 4^k) < \varepsilon$ and so both sets \mathcal{R}_1 and \mathcal{R}_2 contain subsets of density greater than $1/8 - \varepsilon$. The set \mathcal{R}_0 has density 0 and the congruence class $5 \pmod{8}$ has density $1/4$ with respect to Ω . Applying Lemma 5 with $X = \Omega$, $W = \{m > 1 : m \equiv 5 \pmod{8}\}$, $t = 2$, and $\alpha_1 = \alpha_2 = 1/8$ to the partition $5 \pmod{8} = \mathcal{R}_0 \cup \mathcal{R}_1 \cup \mathcal{R}_2$, we see that \mathcal{R}_1 has density $1/8$ and \mathcal{R}_2 has density $1/8$. This completes the proof. \square

5. Some Impossible Permutation Patterns for Quadruples

By Theorem 1, every triple permutation pattern is the permutation pattern of triples $(m, S(m), S^2(m))$ of the iterated Syracuse function for a set of integers m of positive density. The story for quadruple permutation patterns is different. In this section we prove that there are quadruple permutation patterns that never occur as permutation patterns of quadruples $(m, S(m), S^2(m), S^3(m))$ of the iterated Syracuse function.

Theorem 5. *Consider quadruples*

$$(m, S(m), S^2(m), S^3(m))$$

such that $S^i(m) \neq S^j(m)$ for $i \neq j$ and the triple $(m, S(m), S^2(m))$ has permutation pattern $(1, 2, 3)$, that is,

$$m < S(m) < S^2(m).$$

For these quadruples there are four possible quadruple permutation patterns:

$$(1, 2, 3, 4), \quad (1, 2, 4, 3), \quad (2, 3, 4, 1), \quad (1, 3, 4, 2).$$

The density of each of these permutation patterns is as follows:

<i>permutation pattern $\sigma \in \Sigma_4$</i>	<i>permutation density $d_4(\sigma)$</i>
$(1, 2, 3, 4)$	$1/8$
$(1, 2, 4, 3)$	$1/16$
$(2, 3, 4, 1)$	$1/16$
$(1, 3, 4, 2)$	0

Moreover, the permutation pattern $(1, 3, 4, 2)$ never occurs.

Note that $1/4 = 1/8 + 1/16 + 1/16$ is the Syracuse function permutation pattern density of the triple $(1, 2, 3)$.

Proof. By Theorems 3 and 4, we have $m < S(m) < S^2(m)$ if and only if

$$m \equiv 7 \pmod{8}.$$

Then $m = 7 + 8x$ for some nonnegative integer x and

$$m = 7 + 8x < S(m) = 11 + 12x < S^2(m) = 17 + 18x.$$

It follows that

$$S^3(m) = \frac{26 + 27x}{2^e}$$

for some nonnegative integer e .

The congruence class $7 \pmod{8}$ is the disjoint union of the congruence classes $15 \pmod{16}$, $7 \pmod{32}$, and $23 \pmod{32}$.

If $m \equiv 15 \pmod{16}$, then the integers x and $26 + 27x$ are odd and so $e = 0$. We have

$$m < S(m) < S^2(m) = 17 + 18x < 26 + 27x = S^3(x)$$

and so the quadruple $(m, S(m), S^2(m), S^3(m))$ has permutation pattern $(1, 2, 3, 4)$.

If $m \equiv 7 \pmod{32}$, then $x = 4y$ and $e = 1$. We obtain

$$S^3(m) = \frac{26 + 27x}{2} = 13 + 54y = 13 + \left(\frac{27}{2}\right)x.$$

The inequality

$$7 + 8x < 11 + 12x < 13 + \left(\frac{27}{2}\right)x < 17 + 18x$$

implies

$$m < S(m) < S^3(m) < S^2(m).$$

The quadruple $(m, S(m), S^2(m), S^3(m))$ has permutation pattern $(1, 2, 4, 3)$.

If $m \equiv 23 \pmod{32}$, then $x = 2 + 4y$ and $e \geq 2$.

$$\begin{aligned} S^3(m) &= \frac{26 + 27x}{2^e} = \frac{80 + 27 \cdot 4y}{2^e} = \frac{20 + 27y}{2^{e-2}} \\ &\leq 20 + 27y = 20 + 27 \left(\frac{x-2}{4} \right) \\ &= \frac{13}{2} + \left(\frac{27}{4} \right) x < 7 + 8x = m. \end{aligned}$$

The quadruple $(m, S(m), S^2(m), S^3(m))$ has permutation pattern $(2, 3, 4, 1)$.

We see that the permutation pattern $(1, 3, 4, 2)$ never occurs, and that the permutation patterns $(1, 2, 3, 4)$, $(1, 2, 4, 3)$, and $(2, 3, 4, 1)$ have permutation densities $1/8$, $1/16$, and $1/16$, respectively. This completes the proof. \square

Theorem 6. *Consider quadruples*

$$(m, S(m), S^2(m), S^3(m))$$

such that $S^i(m) \neq S^j(m)$ for $i \neq j$ and the triple $(m, S(m), S^2(m))$ has permutation pattern $(1, 3, 2)$, that is,

$$m < S^2(m) < S(m).$$

For these quadruples there are four possible quadruple permutation patterns:

$$(1, 3, 2, 4), \quad (2, 4, 3, 1), \quad (1, 4, 2, 3), \quad (1, 4, 3, 2).$$

The density of each of these permutation patterns is as follows:

permutation pattern $\sigma \in \Sigma_4$	permutation density $d_4(\sigma)$
$(1, 3, 2, 4)$	$1/16$
$(2, 4, 3, 1)$	$1/16$
$(1, 4, 2, 3)$	0
$(1, 4, 3, 2)$	0

Moreover, the permutation patterns $(1, 4, 3, 2)$ and $(1, 4, 2, 3)$ never occur.

Note that $1/8 = 1/16 + 1/16$ is the Syracuse function permutation pattern density of the triple $(1, 3, 2)$.

Proof. By Theorems 3 and 4, we have $m < S^2(m) < S(m)$ if and only if

$$m \equiv 11 \pmod{16}.$$

Then $m = 11 + 16x$ for some nonnegative integer x and

$$m = 11 + 16x < S^2(m) = 13 + 18x < S(m) = 17 + 24x.$$

It follows that

$$S^3(m) = \frac{20 + 27x}{2^e}$$

for some nonnegative integer e .

The congruence class $11 \pmod{16}$ is the disjoint union of the congruence classes $11 \pmod{32}$ and $27 \pmod{32}$.

If $m \equiv 27 \pmod{32}$, then x and $20 + 27x$ are odd and so $e = 0$. We have

$$S(m) = 17 + 24x < 20 + 27x = S^3(m)$$

and the quadruple $(m, S(m), S^2(m), S^3(m))$ has permutation pattern $(1, 3, 2, 4)$.

If $m \equiv 11 \pmod{32}$, then x is even and $e \geq 1$. We obtain

$$S^3(m) = \frac{20 + 27x}{2^e} \leq 10 + \left(\frac{27}{2}\right)x < 11 + 16x = m.$$

The quadruple $(m, S(m), S^2(m), S^3(m))$ has permutation pattern $(2, 4, 3, 1)$.

We see that the permutation patterns $(1, 4, 3, 2)$ and $(1, 4, 2, 3)$ never occur and that each of the permutation patterns $(1, 3, 2, 4)$ and $(2, 4, 3, 1)$ has density $1/16$. This completes the proof. \square

Theorem 7. Consider quadruples

$$(m, S(m), S^2(m), S^3(m))$$

such that $S^i(m) \neq S^j(m)$ for $i \neq j$ and the triple $(m, S(m), S^2(m))$ has permutation pattern $(2, 1, 3)$, that is,

$$S(m) < m < S^2(m).$$

For these quadruples there are four possible quadruple permutation patterns:

$$(2, 1, 3, 4), \quad (2, 1, 4, 3), \quad (3, 1, 4, 2), \quad (3, 2, 4, 1).$$

The density of each of these permutation patterns is as follows:

permutation pattern $\sigma \in \Sigma_4$	permutation density $d_4(\sigma)$
$(2, 1, 3, 4)$	$1/16$
$(3, 1, 4, 2)$	$1/32$
$(3, 2, 4, 1)$	$1/32$
$(2, 1, 4, 3)$	0

Moreover, the permutation pattern $(2, 1, 4, 3)$ never occurs.

Note that $1/8 = 1/16 + 1/32 + 1/32$ is the Syracuse function permutation pattern density of the triple $(2, 1, 3)$.

Proof. By Theorems 3 and 4, we have $S(m) < m < S^2(m)$ if and only if

$$m \equiv 9 \pmod{16}.$$

Then $m = 9 + 16x$ for some nonnegative integer x and

$$S(m) = 7 + 12x < m = 9 + 16x < S^2(m) = 11 + 18x.$$

It follows that

$$S^3(m) = \frac{17 + 27x}{2^e}$$

for some nonnegative integer e .

The congruence class $9 \pmod{16}$ is the disjoint union of the congruence classes $9 \pmod{32}$, $25 \pmod{64}$, and $57 \pmod{64}$.

If $m \equiv 9 \pmod{32}$, then x is even, $17 + 27x$ is odd, and so $e = 0$. We have

$$S^2(m) = 11 + 18x < S^3(m) = 17 + 27x$$

and the quadruple $(m, S(m), S^2(m), S^3(m))$ has permutation pattern $(2, 1, 3, 4)$.

If $m \equiv 57 \pmod{64}$, then $x = 3 + 4y$ and $e = 1$. We obtain

$$\begin{aligned} S^3(m) &= \frac{17 + 27(3 + 4y)}{2} = 49 + 54y \\ &= 49 + 54 \left(\frac{x - 3}{4} \right) = \frac{17}{2} + \left(\frac{27}{2} \right) x. \end{aligned}$$

The inequality

$$7 + 12x < \frac{17}{2} + \left(\frac{27}{2}\right)x < 9 + 16x$$

implies

$$S(m) < S^3(m) < m < S^2(m).$$

The quadruple $(m, S(m), S^2(m), S^3(m))$ has permutation pattern $(3, 1, 4, 2)$.

If $m \equiv 25 \pmod{64}$, then $x = 1 + 4y$ and $e \geq 2$. We obtain

$$\begin{aligned} S^3(m) &= \frac{17 + 27(1 + 4y)}{2^e} = \frac{11 + 27y}{2^{e-2}} \\ &\leq 11 + 27y = 11 + 27\left(\frac{x-1}{4}\right) = \frac{17}{4} + \left(\frac{27}{4}\right)x \\ &< 7 + 12x = S(m). \end{aligned}$$

The quadruple $(m, S(m), S^2(m), S^3(m))$ has permutation pattern $(3, 2, 4, 1)$.

We see that the permutation pattern $(2, 1, 4, 3)$ never occurs, and that the permutation patterns $(2, 1, 3, 4)$, $(3, 1, 4, 2)$, and $(3, 2, 4, 1)$ have densities $1/16$, $1/32$, and $1/32$, respectively. This completes the proof. \square

6. Dropping Time

An odd integer $m > 1$ has *dropping time* $D(m) = k$ if k is the smallest positive integer such that $S^k(m) < m$, and dropping time $D(m) = \infty$ if $S^k(m) > m$ for all positive integers k . The Collatz conjecture is equivalent to the statement that $D(m) < \infty$ for all odd integers $m > 1$. We have $D(m) > k$ if and only if $S^i(m) \neq 1$ for all $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, k\}$ and the permutation pattern of the $(k + 1)$ -tuple $(m, S(m), S^2(m), \dots, S^k(m))$ is not of the form $(1, a_2, a_3, \dots, a_{k+1})$, where $(a_2, a_3, \dots, a_{k+1})$ is any permutation of $(2, 3, \dots, k + 1)$.

Theorem 8. *Let $N_k(x)$ count the number of odd integers $m \leq x$ such that $D(m) \leq k$. Then*

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{N}_1 &= \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \frac{N_1(x)}{x/2} = \frac{1}{2} \\ \bar{N}_2 &= \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \frac{N_2(x)}{x/2} = \frac{5}{8} \\ \bar{N}_3 &= \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \frac{N_3(x)}{x/2} = \frac{3}{4} \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Permutation pattern densities give explicit values for $N_k(x)$ for $k = 1, 2$, and 3 . An odd integer $m > 1$ has dropping time $D(m) = 1$ if and only if $S(m) < m$

if and only if the pair $(m, S(m))$ has permutation pattern $(2, 1)$, and so \overline{N}_1 is the density of the permutation pattern $(2, 1)$. We have $\overline{N}_1 = 1/2$ by Theorem 2.

The odd integer $m > 1$ has dropping time $D(m) \leq 2$ if and only if the permutation pattern of the triple $(m, S(m), S^2(m))$ is not $(1, 2, 3)$ or $(1, 3, 2)$. By Theorem 1, the permutation pattern $(1, 2, 3)$ has density $1/4$ and the permutation pattern $(1, 3, 2)$ has density $1/8$. Therefore, $\overline{N}_2 = 1 - 1/4 - 1/8 = 5/8$.

The odd integer $m > 1$ has dropping time $D(m) \leq 3$ if and only if the quadruple $(m, S(m), S^2(m), S^3(m))$ has permutation pattern not equal to $(1, a_2, a_3, a_4)$, where (a_2, a_3, a_4) is any of the six permutations of 2, 3, and 4. By Theorems 5 and 6, the sum of the densities of these six permutation patterns is $1/4$ and so $\overline{N}_3 = 1 - 1/4 = 3/4$. \square

The dropping time function is the Syracuse function analogue of the stopping time function of Riho Terras [10]. It would be of interest to prove (similar to results of Terras) that the limit

$$\overline{N}_k = \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \frac{N_k(x)}{x/2}$$

exists for all positive integers k and that

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \overline{N}_k = 1.$$

Acknowledgement. I thank Yosef Berman (CUNY Graduate Center) for computer calculations of permutation patterns for triples and quadruples of the iterated Syracuse function $S(m)$ that motivated this paper.

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